

Standing Against to Workplace Discrimination (In the Name of Law & Order, Humanity, Religion, and Better Management): A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: Rational judgments and decisions should be based on solid logic and rationale as well as numeric variables. On the other hand, irrational judgments and decisions rely on feelings, linguistic variables. Appointed executives who manage acting businesses must demonstrate solid logic, numeric and linguistic justifications for their decisions to the stakeholders: business owners, government, share-stakeholders. The study examines the justification and logic of the four main factors why humanity fights against discrimination during the promotion: legally, humanitarian reasons, religious grounds, and administrative reasons. The study strongly suggests that discrimination during the promotion is against the law, religion, humanity, and efficient management. For these reasons, honest, fair people and organizations have to fight against discrimination; in the name of law, in the name of religion, in the name of humanity, and in the name of managerial efficiency. Discriminators, who are unfairly making the lives of innocent employees, their children, and partners hell, have to be punished by the law, religion, humanity, and management for realizing humanistic and holistic justice.

KEYWORDS: Discrimination at Workplace during Promotion stage, worthiness, jurisdictional, humanitarian, Religious, and Managerial perspective

1 INTRODUCTION

Discrimination can be defined as taking and executing unfair decisions that harm the rights and interests of the victims on an unequal basis. Discrimination is a collection of decisions and actions that must be prevented and inhibited. There are many different definitions of discrimination and many studies on them. Although discrimination in the promotion stage is often encountered in real life in the workplace (because of camouflage called managerial decision), it does not attract as much attention as other discriminations.

The carrot stick theorem assumes that punishment and reward systems prevent unfair, bad decisions and actions and promote fair decisions and actions. This literature study has been examined four main factors affecting discrimination; legal, religious, humanitarian, and administrative aspects. Turkish culture associates encouraging and inhibiting elements with "fear of God" and "shame from people." For those who will commit crimes and evil deeds, the phrase "he is not ashamed of the servant, he is not afraid of God" is used. Fear or love of God is considered an element that encourages people for good or prevents them from evil. The law of God and the law of people (religion and law), both contain religious motifs, are essential elements that affect people's decisions and actions. Human dignity assumes that people must live in good conditions in terms of physically and spiritually. Human dignity is also suggesting employees have to be promoted fairly; without discrimination. The fourth and final element is the managerial perspective of discrimination.

In addition to managerial efficiency, management is a job that requires care and attention based on fairness and respect to jurisdictional rules and regulations. A manager has to give adequate care and attention to the requirements of the job. Professional managers, by proxy on behalf of the state (citizens) or business owners (them), manage organizations. Citizens give power of attorney to the administrators. The owner of public institutions and organizations in the state, the owner of the state, is citizens. Business owners delegate their management rights to managers by proxy. A power of attorney is given to people who have sufficient legal, administrative, and conscientious qualifications. The most crucial essential condition of being a deputy manager is to protect the rights and interests of the person and institutions that he is a proxy with his decisions and actions. A

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manager makes decisions (including promotion decisions) on behalf of business owners, government, employees by proxy. Violation of the agreement by discriminatory decisions means acting against the deal, which generally should result in the superstition of the contract. Managers (those who assume the right of management by proxy) should also act fairly, equitably and protect business owners' interests in their promotion decisions. Irregularities such as discrimination based on religion, language, race, class, nepotism, cheating, bribery while making promotion decisions are unacceptable crimes for professional managers.

Discrimination can be accepted up to a point in sole proprietorships. For instance, management can promote and appoint an unqualified relative as a manager in the self-owned company, even though he is not qualified by favoring and making discrimination. As long as decision-makers bear the consequences (loss, bankruptcy) of the decision, it can be tolerated.

On the other hand (in the public sector), such unfair decisions cannot be tolerated; since employing an unqualified manager in the company is a betrayal of the Proxy agreement made with government or business owners. Because in public companies, the business owner is the citizen; if there is loss, the party that suffers the damage is the citizen (give a power of attorney) and not the decision-taker (proxy). In other words, instead of the responsible body: authority, non-responsible bodies may suffer from wrongdoing or crime. Similar unfair decision(s) during the promotion can also be (should be) considered an abuse of power of attorney: a crime.

Beyond these, mismanagement of the business by incompetent and favored people prevents the business from reaching its goals, profit, and market share. The government may collect less tax than it should. Finally, and most importantly, if the business is not managed well, the competitiveness of the business and the country may decrease. For all these reasons, the promotion decisions of professional managers are decisions that can (and should) not accept mistakes or cheats.

Today, discrimination at the promotion stage is a serious complaint in small and large enterprises, in our country, in developed and developing countries. Discrimination during the promotion was there for centuries. However, the study examines discrimination from four different perspectives. Studies on sub-subjects of discrimination, opposing views, and different perspectives can enrich scientific knowledge.

2. TYPES AND DEFINITIONS OF DISCRIMINATION

in the literature, many different types and definitions of discrimination are listed. In this article, discrimination is defined as transferring the rights and interests of innocent people; who deserve them on a fair, justifiable, and measurable basis to those who do not deserve them on a reasonable, justifiable, and measurable basis.

Discrimination during the promotion stage can be defined as transferring the promotion rights and interests of innocent people; who deserve them on a fair, justifiable, and measurable basis to those who do not deserve them on a reasonable, justifiable and quantifiable basis.

There are other definitions such as Subtle or Covert Discrimination: King and Ahmad (2010) examined covert and indirect discrimination in their study. Covert discrimination is defined as decisions and behaviors that cannot be determined directly by the law but negatively affect the victims' working conditions.

Burkard, Boticki, and Madson (2002) defined five scales used on discrimination, prejudice, and diversity in their study. These are:

- (1) James K, Lovato C, and Cropanzano (1994) 's inventory of prejudice/discrimination in the workplace: the Workplace Prejudice/Discrimination Inventory (WPDI). This inventory was developed based on social identity theory. The inventory, which aims to reveal the views of individuals on discrimination and prejudice in the workplace, consists of 15 questions containing a 7-point Likert scale.
- (2) Montei and Eggers' (1996) The Attitudes Toward Diversity Scale (ATDS).
- (3) The Organizational Diversity Inventory (ODI) by Hegarty and Dalton (1995)
- (4) Larkey's (1996) Employee Diversity Questionnaire (WDQ) and
- (5) Chung and Harmon's (1999) The Perceived Occupational Opportunity Scale and the Perceived Occupational Discrimination Scale (PODS)–Form B.

On the other hand, Kelman (1991) defined discrimination in general skill job tests in four main classes in his study. These are; (1) static discrimination, (2) dynamic discrimination, (3) distribution discrimination (4) discrimination based on production costs and production quantities.

2.1. Static Discrimination: There's no visible discrimination insight. However, depending on the situation, the test's shape or style is being changed. For example, when white employees who will be favored at the moment of promotion need to be. For example, when white employees who will be favored at the moment of promotion need to be promoted (when whites apply), they are

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promoted by lottery. They're blocking the promotion of black people with a heavy test when there are many black people. Therefore, blacks cannot get the promotion, high salary, status they deserve. There is no injustice, no discrimination, but one person or group is unfairly losing interests while the others are making a fortune with unjustified and unfair decisions. The author (Kelman 1991) argues that such discriminations activities and decisions should be considered intentional (crime) or gross negligence.

2.2. Dynamic Discrimination; is Regulating the exam's conditions, place, and time so that the discriminated candidate will fail. Besides making noise and (sexual, psychological) harassment can also be considered as dynamic discrimination. Kelman (1991) classified dynamic discrimination under three headings. These are Illegitimate Discrimination, Inadequate Training, and Organizational Reform.

2.2.1. Illegitimate Discrimination; Reduces performance. For example, sexual harassment of women reduces their performance—a woman who has to deal with harassment. Even if the promotional test and criteria are reasonable, she can't concentrate on her work. The performance of the female employee decreases due to unlawfulness (failure to protect the integrity and body integrity of the employee). The employer may not be guilty of wrongdoing in the exam or evaluation but can be responsible for their inability to protect female employees from sexual harassment. In such cases, the results of job tests are not a valuable factor that can be used in promotion decisions; there is dynamic discrimination. Women should not suffer, and their promotions should not be blocked due to the inadequacy or malice of their bosses. By law, employers are responsible for ensuring ideal working conditions. The author is divided into three. These are unlawful discrimination, unequal education, organizational reforms.

2.2.2. Inadequate Training: Training and practice are factors that directly affect the quality of work and the amount of production. If an employee is trained for a long time about the exam subject than others, it is inadequate training during the promotion stage. Fairness is to provide equal rights education to all employees as much as possible. Equal rights (time, lecturers, place, etc.) should be delivered in education to all employees for fairness.

2.2.3. Organizational Reform: One might prefer to call such discrimination "polished discrimination." Reducing the opportunity of victims and increasing the chance of favored employees by changing the promotion criteria with the organizational reform excuse. It is a common exercise in developing countries. The employer announces institution will be reformed. If the name of the organization is changed, it is said that the restructuring will be made. Reform can be called giving young people a chance at management. But:

by chance, this reform will be implemented in only one targeted department.

by chance, old managers in the other department, decision-makers, stay in their chairs,

by chance, the newly appointed manager is the relative of one of the wealthiest people in the area, by the chance

by chance, company management is a close friend of one of the richest people in the area,

by chance, in every department, the experience was a pre-condition; this time, youth is the pre-condition,

by chance, these reform activities are needed at once, no need to do it again.

According to perpetrators, such polished discrimination is not discrimination; it is only reform. But with this reform, the peoples' right to promote might have been butchered, who has been working in the department for decades. Victims' hundreds of salaries and bonuses, partner's and children's earnings all are chopped and minced slowly and painfully. It is a good excuse for the perpetrators. Such detailed, planned, and carefully executed activities can be and should be considered as organized crime. Such an organized crime that perpetrators can hide the result of their original highly illegal activities, and perpetrators can even brag and gloat with these polished activities.

2.3. Distributive Discrimination: Particular (religious, racial) groups may provide a majority in specific geographic regions, cities, and organizations. Majority power may offer them an inequitable advantage over minority groups. Distribution-based discrimination is classified under three main headings by Kelman (1991).

2.3.1. Skepticism About Productivity: Employees naturally may not be productive because of their religion, race, language, and gender. For example, a Muslim employee's productivity in producing pork, including foods, would be very skeptical. This skepticism might reduce his chance in the food company for promotion in the non-Muslim country. At the same time, it can be an advantage in a Muslim country. Similarly, a lady's productivity would be very much skeptical in carrying goods as a porter. Indeed, such skepticism would reduce their chances during the promotion and/or other managerial decisions.

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2.3.2. Subsidy Arguments: Another factor influencing discrimination is subsidies from states or consumer societies etc. The employment or promotion of a protected group is, indeed, can be unfair discrimination, including promotion decisions, against others.

2.3.3. Reparations: Employers or any other citizens have to pay compensation if they do not comply with legal requirements. The amount of payment can be a very critical criterion in changing the destructive behaviors of management. Naturally, high compensation and repatriation can be a high cost and, consequently, a big motivation to make good and fair decisions. Whereas low compensation, repatriation can be unimportant costs and hence unimportant motivations to make good and fair decisions. A real-life experience clearly, exhibits this logic. One day a person is caught by law enforcement while gambling in the street. During the jurisdiction, he accepted his wrongdoing, and he tried to pay the fine, but the prosecution tried to solve other cases and asked about another bad doing did you second bad doing he said no I did not, and officials wanted to question him further he accepted the accusation even though he did not do it. He said, "indeed, I did not make the second allegation whenever he has been asked. I accepted it because the fine was so small that I would pay the money and go; otherwise, they would keep me longer and punish longer.

It is believed that repatriation or punishment should be much higher than the unfair earning; therefore, criminals may stop unfair wrongdoings. the actual repatriation would be making a loss in the company and going for bankruptcy

2.3.4. The Input Cost vs. Employee Output Distinction: Individual Output Centered Discrimination: The primary purpose of commercial enterprises is to make a profit. The profit is the difference between revenue and cost. The difference between the costs incurred for an employee and the return or benefit earned from that employee (cost-benefit relationship) should be the basis of the fair promotion decision. However, discriminated employees' or institutions' costs might be unfairly increased while the same employees' or institutions' earnings are reduced. This would be classified as discrimination based on the cost-benefit relationship.

3. DISCRIMINATION AT WORKPLACE

Santora and Seaton (2008) suggest, age-based discrimination still exists in the workplace; some companies have listed the reasons for age discrimination as financial burdens, costs, personal responsibilities, harassment, and the need to reach the correct size.

In addition to age discrimination, gender discrimination is also a vital subject in the workplace and for Entrepreneurship. Somuncu, Ilter, Yilmaz, and Kaymaz (2015) investigated the Factors That Hinder Women's Entrepreneurship in the Accounting Profession. According to Hultin's (1998) 2017 employer-covering study in Switzerland, women, and men with job market positions with similar family situations have a lower chance of becoming managers, especially in the private sector. The same study showed that the notion that "women have less authority: enforcement power, even if they are managers" is rejected. In other words, although women have a similar level of authority, women are given less chance by excused for lack of authority.

Hultin's (1998) 2017 employer-involving study in Switzerland represents, in men and women with similar family situations and job market positions, Women have less chance of becoming managers, especially in the private sector. The same study showed that the prejudice "women have less authority, even if they are managers" is not correct. In other words, although women have a similar level of authority, women are given less chance by excused for lack of authority.

According to Wolf and Fligstein (1979), authority is the degree of legitimate control over other employees. Autonomy is the degree of freedom of employees in the workplace.

In the workplace, whenever authority increases, control also increases; on the other hand, autonomy decreases. If authority decreases, the degree of control of the manager decreases, and autonomy, freedom, increase. The administrative authority in the workplace is the authority to direct and control the workplace in accordance with the workplace objectives. If an employee's movements, decisions, and activities are limited within the framework of administrative authority, the employee's skills performance may be severely limited.

According to Wright et al. (1995); Imbalances in the hierarchy of authority or power can be considered the source of inequalities in the workplace, injustices, and consequences.

According to Ghumman et al. (2013), (1) legal loopholes, (2) increased religious diversity in America, (3) increased freedom to express religious beliefs, and (4) the unique nature of religions have contributed to increased discrimination in the workplace.

Discrimination against Muslims during job applications was examined as an experimental field study by King and Ahmad (2010). Jolson (1974) examined workplace discrimination against Jews based on marketing. Hodge (2006) examined discrimination against evangelic Christians in different educational environments. Thyer and Myers (2009) examined how a hostile working

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environment is used in religious discrimination. The Equal Employment Opportunity Commission (EEOC 2011) found that in the past decade, accusations of religious discrimination increased by 96% between 2000 and 2010.

Studies on discrimination make it clear discrimination in the workplace is quite a diverse and widespread issue. Studies also show that discrimination has existed throughout history, continuing with even more complexities, and it is becoming more challenging to uncover and prove it.

3.1. Discrimination During Promotion

Any decision that is not based on fairness will create victims and/or victims. However, discrimination, including unfair decisions during the promotion, is different from others in terms of continuity. While other discrimination decisions often victimize victims once or twice, unfair discrimination decisions taken during promotion victimize their victims for days, months, even years, many times (for example, the hourly wage difference would victimize the victim once a day, five times a week twenty times a month and 200 times a year and maybe 1000 times in five years).

3.1.1. Victimization of Employees. The increase in the per-piece wage paid according to the daily production can seriously affect the salary of employees who victimize the victim financially many times. Similarly, the mental feelings of the employee; His faith in humanity, in God, in law, can be destroyed. Such social developments can also endanger peace in the workplace and threaten peace in society.

3.1.2 Loses of Company and Shareholders. Hard-working clever employees can resign and leave the job whenever they face discrimination. Or they can get demoralized and work much below their actual performance. As a result, production at work and consequently profitability would go down; hence company and shareholders all suffer.

3.1.3 Loses of Government and Third Parties. The victimization of employees endangers peace in the workplace and in public. Government cannot collect necessary taxes at the rate it expects from non-competitive workplaces that do not work well. Losing or Having trouble with well-trained and highly skilled employees can reduce product quality, which means losing competitiveness. Government cannot collect the necessary tax from uncompetitive companies, where discrimination, unhappiness, and conflicts exist than competitive companies. Beyond that, banks would not like to work with poorly managed because of discrimination. Working and/or not working with poorly managed companies will reduce the size and profitability of banks. Customers have to deal with less quality goods and services. All other stakeholders also receive their share of mismanagement. From a managerial point of view, discrimination in decisions at the promotional stage is even more harmful than the different types of Discrimination, Whether or not it is Conscious Discrimination.

3.1.4 Moral Responsibility. Milton Friedman (1970) stated that one of the responsibilities of a company manager is to comply with the basic moral traditions (social responsibilities) of society as well as generate profit.

The Social Accountability 8000 Standard (SA 8000) is modeled under ISO 9000 management system standards. This standard designed the management policies for social (moral) standards under different categories. These categories are child labor, forced labor, health and safety, collective bargaining and union rights, and other discrimination issues.

4. EXAMINING THE WORKPLACE DISCRIMINATION IN TERMS OF LEGAL, HUMANITARIAN, RELIGIOUS, AND ADMINISTRATIVE PERSPECTIVES

During a visit to the University of George August Göttingen within the framework of the Erasmus exchange program, an experiment was conducted. In the experiment, 12 participants were asked to donate a certain amount of money to other participants regardless of any rules when their turn came. Everyone was given a chance to give and receive equal amounts of money. It was guaranteed that all transactions would not be disclosed. After a certain number of transactions are performed, it has been observed that participants who have received constant help did not help others. They did not help at all the others but took all the money. The others were left without money: the (economic) system was collapsed. Egoist participants won everything, while non-egotists lost all their money. When asked about the losers, they said: "system was unfair, their good intentions had been abused, and most importantly, they lost their faith to the game (system), and they would no longer help in these circumstances. A similar reaction by another person who lost his faith in his believes. He claimed that he would never ever provide food aid to poor people. Because a bus driver from a village attached him without any reason, he claimed he lost his faith in humanity, law & order, and religion. Naturally, there will be problems in the systems where transactions are not open. There are no balances and no fairness. Even though the experiment wasn't real, Charity lovers who lost all their money said they were deceived, angry they said they would not help the others. Interestingly, they have been called vengeful.

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The rules changed in the second phase of the experiment: the two people who have helped the most and the two who have supported the least will be announced publicly. The experiment was repeated. Participants who did not help in the first round are now started to help a little bit. The system; Money flow, the economic cycle worked for longer. The vigilante group, embarrassed by the public declaration, had started to help with the results announcement. One of the main elements of management is openness and the sense of shame attached to the experiment, which encouraged or forced people to behave more humanely and fairly.

In the third phase of the experiment, the rules changed once again. This time, participants who made less than the average amount of aid were told that half their money would be confiscated. This time, almost all participants started to pay more for help to others; now, their goal was to exceed the average amount of aid to the others. The volume of transactions has increased more in the system. The game (or economic transformation) has become permanent. So, openness, sense of shame, and fear of punishment can be the essential elements of running a fair system (in this case, game).

The proverb "(a person who) is not ashamed of servants and is not afraid of God" (can do any kind of wrongdoing)" explains the situation very well. According to this logic, the essential elements that prevent people's immoral and criminal behaviors and decisions are: being ashamed of humanity, being ashamed & fear of law & order, and finally, fear from God. This study argues that the main elements that can keep people away from discrimination and lawlessness are: being ashamed or fearing the law, humanity, and religion. Besides, the urge for managerial success can also be another factor preventing decision-makers from discrimination and lawlessness.

4.1. Legally Perspective Of Discrimination

Legal rules and regulations contribute to the management in a fair and orderly manner. "Law and order" have been considered as a base for democracy and justice. Many books have been written, and films have been produced on "Law and order." Discrimination fundamentally opposes the concepts of law, justice, and order. For this reason, governance philosophy aiming at law, justice, and order, has to resist and fight discrimination.

International law and many local and legal systems oppose and prohibit discrimination and discrimination in the workplace during the promotion with law, conventions, and sub-clauses.

According to United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948), articles related to discrimination are stated in articles 1, 2, and 7.

Article 1 "All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and should act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood".

Article 2 "Everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms outlined in this declaration, without distinction of any kind, such as race, color, sex, language, religion, political or other opinions, national or social origin, property, birth, or another status. Furthermore, no distinction shall be made based on the political, jurisdictional, or international status of the country or territory to which a person belongs, whether it be independent, trust, non-self-governing or under any other limitation of sovereignty."

Article 7 "All are equal before the law and are entitled without any discrimination to equal protection of the law. All are entitled to equal protection against any discrimination in violation of this declaration and against any incitement to such discrimination."

International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (entry into force 3 January 1976)

Article 6-1. "The States Parties to the present Covenant recognize the right to work, which includes the right of everyone to the opportunity to gain his living by work which he freely chooses or accepts, and will take appropriate steps to safeguard this right." Of course, these equal opportunities in the work environment should include promotion decisions.

Article 7-a (i) Fair wages and equal remuneration for work of equal value without distinction of any kind, in particular women being guaranteed conditions of work not inferior to those enjoyed by men, with equal pay for equal work;" Fair wages and equal remuneration is very much related with promotion decisions.

According to article 14 of the European Convention on Human Rights (Rome, 4.XI.1950), discrimination is prohibited "The enjoyment of the rights and freedoms outlined in this Convention shall be secured without discrimination on any ground such as sex, race, color, language, religion, political or other opinions, national or social origin, association with a national minority, property, birth or another status." Including discrimination in the workplace and discrimination during the promotion. In the European Summit in Lisbon on 22 and 23 July 2007, it was decided to improve human rights conditions further.

The 1st article of the American Convention on Human Rights "Pact of San Jose, Costa Rica" "The States Parties to this Convention undertake to respect the rights and freedoms recognized herein and to ensure to all persons subject to their

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jurisdiction the free and full exercise of those rights and freedoms, without any discrimination for reasons of race, color, sex, language, religion, political or another opinion, national or social origin, economic status, birth, or any other social condition.

Discrimination in the workplace has taken its place in labor law as well. For instance: The General Conference of the International Labour Organization has been convened at Geneva by the Governing Body of the International Labour Office; Convention No. 111. According to convention article 1 (a), discrimination is defined as "any distinction, exclusion or preference made based on race, color, sex, religion, political opinion, national extraction or social origin, which has the effect of nullifying or impairing equality of opportunity or treatment in employment or occupation." 2nd article of the same convention says, "Any distinction, exclusion or preference in respect of a particular job based on the inherent requirements thereof shall not be deemed to be discrimination." Again, the same conventions 3rd article says, "Each Member for which this convention is in force undertakes, by methods appropriate to national conditions and practice — (e) to ensure observance of the policy in the activities of vocational guidance, vocational training, and placement services under the direction of a national authority.

Moreover, constitutions like the Constitution of the Republic of Turkey have articles about discrimination. For instance: Article 10 states that "Everyone is equal in front of the law regardless language, race, color, gender, political thought, philosophical belief, religion, sect and so on."

Turkish Labor Law also includes articles on discrimination and workplace discrimination. Turkish Labor Code Section 2 defined the workplace as places where the goods or services are produced, where business is organized under the same administration (workplace-related locations), resting, breastfeeding, eating, sleeping, washing, examination caring, physical and vocational training activities are achieved. Article 5 stressed that discrimination in business relationships based on language, race, gender, political thought, philosophical belief, religion cannot be achieved. Section 31 of the Turkish Unions law Act 2821. States the recruitment of workers cannot be conditioned on whether or not they enter a particular union or retain membership for a specific union or resign from membership or enter the union or not. The article mentioned above states that there can be no discrimination between employees during recruitment and promotion. In addition to the labor law, paragraph 1 of Article 122 of the Turkish trade law Code No. 5237 states that "anyone shall be sentenced six months to one year to prison or a fined, who linked the employment to one of the situations mentioned above (race, language, religion, sect, nationality, color, gender, etc.).

Karagöz (2012) listed the Conditions for The Implementation of "Equal Conduct responsibility" in his study as follows; 2. The Presence of a Working Community in the Workplace, 3. Legal Conduct of a Collective Nature, 4. Convenience in Time. In fact, it is worth using the word "equal behavior debt" to be fair behavior, because in some cases treating people, with different qualifications, equally can mean being unfair on an equitable basis. In this context, it is worth using the term "fairness" instead of the law's obligation to act equally for justice to be realized.

If the employee is violated as set out in paragraph 6 of Article 5 of the Labor Code, the worker may claim appropriate compensation, up to 4 months' wages, and other rights that they have been deprived of. Karagoz (2012) Listed the Conditions That Qualify for Discrimination Compensation as follows: 1 Situation where equal conduct responsibility cannot be applied in absolute terms: a) in the employee's wages b) in the termination of the employment contract. 2. Situations where equal conduct responsibility can be applied in absolute: a) In the provision of social benefits b) in matters related to the right to management c) in the employment of workers who do not participate in the strike d) in the professional status of the worker.

The legal system is based on justice while deciding on wages: fair remuneration. Based on fairness, there can be wage differences since the abilities of employees, quality of production, fidelity, etc. Obviously, it's not like we're going legal system, legislators, decision-makers: exceptional circumstances, situations, cases; they must make their decisions taking into account the relevant conditions and exceptions; legislators, decision-makers should make their decisions by considering the appropriate conditions, circumstances exceptions; should use their initiatives based on law and justice. An employee who produces high-quality products should be paid higher wages than the employee who makes low-quality products. However, in an environment where both employees make the same quality products, the wage difference creates inequality and injustice. In this context, discrimination compensation should be paid. The employee who produces high-quality products should receive a very high wage, while the low-quality producing employee should receive a lower salary. Whenever high-quality producer employees get lower wages: it is discrimination in the workplace. In this case, discrimination compensation should still be involved.

In his article, Sperino (2011) emphasized the importance of the principle "priority of essence," which is considered one of the basic principles in accounting, law, and management literature, and emphasized that court decisions should be more flexible on this basis.

Priority of essence indicates that a decision-maker (business owner/manager, judge, prosecutor, accountant) has to consider the case's essentials first, rather than procedures and methods. Concentrating too much on procedures and techniques can sometimes cause seeing illusions rather than essentials. In such discrimination cases, judges should use their initiative and neglect the rules

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that give the wrong result, and they should focus on essence: essentials. Sperino (2011) argues that decision-makers in court (juries and judges) should make dynamic decisions based on the principle of priority of the essence, rather than implementing static, existing labor laws on their decisions.

Demiral (2005) argues that Discrimination (rejection of employment application based on sexism) constitutes tort under the law of obligations, and it should be compensated. Within the same logic, an employee's discrimination due to gender, age, and race religion during the promotion phase constitutes a tort-based on the law of obligations. The material and moral grievances faced by the victims due to discrimination during promotion should be compensated by the discriminators. Discrimination in the workplace at the promotion stage is banned and even punished in international institutions, international law, and local laws. In this context:

People (institutions) who believe in and trust in the law must stand and fight against discrimination (including workplace discrimination during promotion) in the name of law and justice.

4.2. Humanitarian Perspective Of Discrimination

The human consequences of discrimination, especially for those discriminated against during the promotional phase, are different legally, materially, and physically; one of the most important consequences can be the breakdown of their human dignity. The humanitarian consequences of discrimination during the promotional phase are different from legal, financial, and physical consequences and maybe more harmful.

A discriminated person is mostly Blamed by the responsible body, like; you are incompetent, you are not clever, you are not intelligent, etc.; even though these acquisitions are not a correct victim cannot prove they are better than a favored person because of managerial performance recordings in the hands of the discriminator. Even if the victim proves; he is an intelligent or hard-working person, there is always another accusation waiting on the list, correct or not. If the first accusation is not valid, the second one would be, even if the second one is not, the third one may be valid. Even if there is no valid accusation, you are a problematic person (list of problems), you have to be fired. Sooner or later employee has to give up and accept the discrimination. But this time, firstly, perpetrators can humiliate the victim: "we beat you," "you lost," "loser." Secondly, even the friends consciously or un-consciously humiliate the victim "you coward: you could not fight with them," "you are weak," "chickened out." In some cases, the victim's family can also humiliate the victim.

One of the victims states the feeling as "I could be able to bear losing money, time, status but I cannot still bear the humiliation I have been faced: it is unbearable." "I wish I would fight with them, but for my family, I couldn't" "humiliation is much worse than losing money, time, status."

Individuals whose honors have been broken lose their hopes; their ambitions; their beliefs. Individuals, societies can survive with their beliefs, hopes, and ambitions. Discrimination not only affects individuals' mental health negatively but also affects public health.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted by the UN General Assembly in 1948, mentioned honorable, equal, inalienable rights humanity has. People cannot transfer or sell these rights of their own will. The concept of human dignity has been started to be used with this declaration. Afterward, the rights and freedoms based on human dignity have been discussed, examined, and developed in literature and legal settings.

Clapham (2006) suggests one of the conditions for human dignity is the creation of conditions in which each person's basic needs will be met. People have to work and earn money in a workplace to meet their needs. Often the wages that people will meet their needs are proportional to the fair promotion at work. So, fair or unjust promotion decisions in the workplace can directly affect human dignity and discrimination.

One of the most outstanding human rights violations committed in the past was committed in Nazi Germany. While racial discrimination rose to its highest level in Nazi Germany, other discriminations, especially discrimination during the promotion in the workplace, were at an all-time high as well. While a group of Nazis considered superior were systematically at the forefront of promotion, others systematically and unequivocally did not get a chance at promotion. Discrimination at the promotion stage is also a crime against humanity, with many discrimination crimes (murders, etc.).

According to Lofaso (2017), employee rights are also considered a human right, and unions traditionally support and protect employees' rights to promotion. In this context, Lofaso (2007) wrote that employee rights should be collected in theory, pointing out the theme of autonomous honorable employees. The author highlighted a need for working with Works Councils, Collective Bargaining, and by considering The Price of Pluralism to identify in a basic theory.

Many definitions have been made for human dignity. But in this study, human dignity is defined as: "The basic rights of Peoples: education, working and living with dignity. Mankind should be able to acquire fundamental rights (education, working,

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and living) with dignity: without begging other persons and institutions, without being oppressed, without compromising their bodies, souls, freedoms, compromising legal and humanitarian rights. Human dignity includes working and promotion, as well. Human dignity in the promotional stage should be without begging other persons and institutions, without being oppressed, without compromising their bodies, souls, freedoms, compromising legal and humanitarian rights. Human dignity also requires equal attention, respect, official and unofficial respectful behaviors. Unequal, unfair, and non-respectful promotion decisions are against humanity and employee dignity.

In the name of human dignity, each individual's difference should be accepted and respected. Employees' different opinions, skills, and independent moral values can be considered an excuse for any kind of discrimination, especially during the promotion.

Skilled employees, core workers, who can provide a competitive advantage to their companies, want respect, want job security, want fair promotion opportunities, and want higher wages. Reduction of Skilled employees who can PROVIDE a competitive advantage because of policies against employee honor reduces the competitiveness of the company and its chances of survival. According to Atkinson (1971), skilled employees who can provide a competitive advantage want job security, fair internal promotion, and higher wages. Unionization is essential in achieving these goals.

Human dignity also includes physical and mental health. In the name of Human dignity, workers' physical and psychological health should be protected. But discrimination, during the promotion can harm the physical and mental health of employees. Many studies examine the effects of discrimination on health.

According to a study by Amaro et al. (1987), Spanish women who do professional work are psychologically stressed by the discrimination they have been faced at work. A similar study by James et al. (1984) examined work-related stress-inducing factors found that Racial Discrimination reveals Africans in North Carolina have health problems with blood pressure. Krieger (1990) found that people of African and Mexican descent who were discriminated at school, at work, while renting a house, receiving medical attention have faced hypertension. Murrell (1996) indicated that there were underweight births because of stress that occurred due to Discrimination in African-American women. Brouwers et al. (2015) suggest that 62.5% of employees who faced discrimination or expected to face discrimination in the work environment have Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) within the 35 countries. A striking result from the same study indicated that almost 60% of participants give up applying for education or training due to expected discrimination. Since they lost their hopes and beliefs. According to this study, even the fear of discrimination causes them to give up their most basic human rights of employment, the right to education, the right to training instinctively.

According to Thorat and Newman (2007), active exclusion through discrimination is not to employ or promote a person or members of a social group even though they have equal or even excellent qualifications than the others (favored ones). According to them, discrimination can be; Market-based Discrimination, professional discrimination, social exclusion.

Market-based discrimination is the inability to enter the entire market or sub-markets due to written or unwritten rules or the inability to be promoted in the market. The employee who has never been introduced into the management market, who has never been given the chance of management experience in the market, even though his managerial knowledge, skills, and capabilities are very high, will not be accepted by the market. Such decisions are usually taken by one prejudiced person and without any ground and explanation. Market-based discriminated people are deprived of work, forced to work with lower wages, unfavorable working conditions, low status.

Professional Discrimination can be defined as favoring members of professional groups and excluding the others. Professional groups (accountants, academicians, medical doctors, lawyers) raise the requirements for new entrants. Still, their own titles remain even though they cannot comply with the new requirements. Thus, the new candidate cannot have a professional title even if they have better professional skills. Hence, less skilled decision-makers can protect their title and benefit from the advantages of the profession in a comfortable way free of professional competition. For instance, the decision-maker, who takes his title by 6 points as soon as he gets the title, may increase the requirements to 100 points for the new applicants. Afterward, they may think that is not enough and increase the requirement by 500 points to keep the title and chair from the others and to stay away from fair, professional competition. With this strategy, rivals would be unwilling, fed up to apply for the promotion. The result of the strategy might keep their market share and chair safe and benefit the earnings and advantages of the profession. The victims' potential results are less salary, fewer sales, fewer bonuses, entirely or partially deprivation of doing the profession, working in unfavorable working conditions, work in a lower status.

Social exclusion: is a complete or partial restriction of victims' participation in economic, educational, and social institutions and activities due to discrimination. Social exclusion deprives victims' certain rights by separating, isolating, embarrassing them based on sub-identities.

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Krieger (1999) examined the concept of inequalities, measures, methods, and health consequences of discrimination. A similar study by Dressler 1990 on colored people indicated that discrimination in the workplace, wage increases, business responsibilities, and total wages during the promotion cause health threats to blood pressure changes.

According to International Criminal Court Status, which has been in force since 2002 (art. 7/1-k), "intentional inhuman acts cause serious suffering or serious damage to physical or mental or physical health" has been considered crimes against humanity. Being discriminated against during the promotional phase has been revealed and proven by scientific studies that cause severe damage to mental or physical health listed above (such as blood pressure, diabetes psychological diseases). Consequently; Discrimination at the promotional stage, which impairs persons or groups' mental or physical health, is a crime against humanity.

4.3. Religious (Islamic) Perspective Of Discrimination

One of the crucial elements that prevent people from doing wrong is religious beliefs. Religious beliefs require fear of God. Those who believe in God fear of his wrath and believe in God. That is why servants are scared of sinning and doing injustice against the other servants and God. Discrimination is a sin because it is unfair: one's right is transferred to another without consent and a fairness base. Justice and the justice of the is the base of main religions. In this study, discrimination will be evaluated only in terms of Islam and its holy book of Kuran (<https://Kuran.Diyanet.Gov.Tr/Tefsir/>). It is better to investigate and assess discrimination in terms of other religions, as well.

In Islam, Bilal-i Habeş is the first prayer, who reads ezan. Even though he was a colored person, there was no discrimination against him due to race. When we look at the Quran, many articles and surahs include writings condemning discrimination and injustice. Some of them are:

NISÂ SURAH 4 / 58 "God commands you to give the relics to competent, and he commands you to rule the people with justice..." The Working contract owner/manager gives relics (tools, raw materials, etc.) to competent (well-trained, experienced, and loyal) employees so that they can take care of business correctly. So, according to Islam, talented people who deserve the promotion or job should be selected in the name of justice, not the favored ones.

In this study, Competency (competent) is evaluated on three bases: Adequate training, experience, and loyalty to the workplace.

TİN SURAH, 95 / 4, by saying, "no doubt We have created the human in a most beautiful way." referred to humans' beauty and dignity, which requires respect. Because of this beauty, humans should be able to live in good conditions; with pride. People should be able to work, earn, and be promoted without being unfairly discriminated against.

ŞEMS SURAH 91 / 13 "The Messenger of God has told them Don't touch to camel (that God has given miraculously) and camel's water" This emphasizes that even a camel has a right to drink water, and this right is also untouchable. Even the Camel should be treated fairly.

A'RÂF SURAH 7/85. "O, my people! make the measurements and weighing correct and with justice; Do not diminish the value of people's goods, do not cause confusion by mischief in the world." The amount of work done by employees in the workplace, quality of products, the difficulty of work, money to be paid all require measurement, weighing, and analysis. In excellent and fair management, measurements and analysis for promotions should be fair. Failure to make correct and fair measurements and weighing can disturb beliefs in law and order in society.

MUTAFFİFİN SURAH 83 /1-3, 1." Woe to those who cheat on measurements and weighing! 2. whenever they measure and buy (something) from the people, they measure it entirely (correctly). 3. But when they give something to them, they measure or weigh the (things) less." Discrimination during the promotion stage primarily includes fraudulent, crooked, and dishonest activities to eat the victims' rights. There is a need for fraudulent, crooked measurements in the quality of the product. That is why they usually change the criterion against the victim, which is mainly related to managerial accounting. It is planned that a study related to this subject will be put into consideration soon. A Final word from Kuran for the fraudulent, crooked, and dishonest people discriminating against innocent victims during promotion "Woe to those who cheat."

BAKARA SURAH 2 / 188. "Do not eat your wealth unjustly among you. Knowingly, by Deviating to sin, don't give some parts of (innocent) peoples' goods to the authorities so that they (authorities) eat it." Discrimination at the promotion stage can be considered unjustly eating (victims') wealth by Deviating to sin. Giving some parts of (innocent) peoples' goods (benefits, salaries, bonuses, bonuses) to the authorities (or others) so that they eat it is clearly discrimination and a sin.

MÂIDE, SURAH 5/8. "They said, "O believers! Keep the truth (justice) alive for Allah, be testified ones with justice. Your hatred of any community should not let you drive to unfairness. Be fair; this is more suitable for religion. Fear from God..." final word "Fear from God" is the main theme of this study. Here, believers are asked to stand against unfairness which is discrimination in this study. Any hostility shouldn't end up with injustice; Discrimination.

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EN'ÂM SURAH 6 / 152. "Do the measurement and weighting with justice. We only hold everyone accountable as much as we can. When you talk about someone, be fair, even if they're close. Keep your promise to God." Even they, your relatives, don't do nepotism; means don't do discriminate against others. According to this surah, people must keep their promise (fairness, non-discrimination, etc.) to God.

Rational decisions; requires precise and fair measurement. Decisions during the promotion stage also require measurement in the name of fairness, openness, and accountability. Cheating and big mistakes in measurement can result in unfairness. Fairness, openness, and accountability in measurements are also very important themes in Islam:

SHU'ARÂ SURAH 26 / 181. "Make the measurement in full. Do not be one giving less (than you should)." 182. "Weigh with the right scale." Indeed, weighing; measuring with the correct scale and criteria is a crucial subject in terms of any mistake or organized in appropriation in it, would result in loss of victim employees' their partners and their children's rights, earnings (rights of worshippers or fundamental human rights).

HADÎD SURAH 57/25. Swear on, with clear miracles; we have sent (downloaded) the book and the ledger (measurement: accounting) so that people realize justice. This surah clearly indicates that there is a clear relationship between (correct and fair) measuring: accounting and realization of (Islamic) justice in Islam. Despite counter suggestions, in Islam, appropriateness, cheatings in measurement, playing with criteria, etc., are the reasons for injustice during the promotion stage in the workplace, and it is forbidden. And to realize Islamic justice, fair measurements and fair accounting should be used. HÛD SURAH 11 / 85. O, my people! "... Do not diminish people's belongings." Similarly, RAHMÂN SURAH 55/ 7. Again, RAHMÂN SURAH 55/ 7. "raised the sky and set the measure." 8. "Do not over mismeasure" 9. "Do the weighting with justice, and hold the scales less."

Cheating on measurement or severe fault in measures results in unfair acquisition. Concerning unfair acquisition, BAKARA SURAH 2 / 188. Do not eat (acquire) of each other's wealth unjustly. Don't give other people's goods by knowingly and sinning so that authorities eat them (as bribery).

NISÂ SURAH 4 / 29. "O, believers! Do not eat your wealth among you in superstition. But it's different if the trade has mutually consented trade. Don't destroy yourself. God is merciful to you." By saying 30. "Whoever does this by crossing the line, unjustly, we will throw him into the Fire of Hell." refers to the unfair acquisition of the rights.

Discrimination during promotion If the employee takes care of orphan children, it can be pretended as the unfair acquisition of orphan children, a severe sin in Islam. Regarding orphan rights, NISÂ SURAH -10 "Those who eat orphans' goods unjustly, will fill their bellies with fire. They already will enter the Blazing Fire." In addition to this, NISÂ SURAH 2 "Give their goods to the orphans, don't trade orphans' clean goods with the dirty ones, do not eat their wealth by adding to your goods; That is a great sin."

Discrimination can be psychological or social brutality for individuals, their families, and orphans. Some of the victims emphasized that real cruelty; brutality is psychological; humiliation rather than monetary or physical. When we talk about cruelty and brutality, BAKARA SURAH 2 / 193 should be read, "Fight them until there is no tyranny or pressure, and the religion is for Allah's. If they stop fighting, yet hostility is only against the cruel people." So, Islam also requires to fight with discrimination and cruel people, including discrimination promotion.

4.4. Administrative Perspective of Discrimination

Discrimination in the workplace, during the promotion, directly affects human capital. Human capital is perhaps the most valuable capital because efficient usage of other capital such as monetary, physical, and political capital depends on the success of human capital. No matter how good economic, physical, political capital, or insufficient human capital is, the lack of or deficiencies in human capital can have zero impact.

The motivation of human capital affects business performance. One of the most important motivations used to motivate employees is to promote them fairly. Using of wordiness (liyakat) criterion during the promotion would be fairer. The wordiness criterion includes three essential elements: wordiness in education, wordiness in terms of experience, and wordiness in loyalty. Loyalty to the organization where money is earned to survive, loyalty to other or hidden organizations can be considered a betrayal. Choices against fairness may diminish enthusiasm to work with loyalty to the organization. Employees will leave the organization, the country, if possible. For developing countries, brain drain is a severe problem. Discrimination can reduce the competitive core competencies of businesses and make them incompatible in today's global world. It can pull the business performance to the bottom.

Discrimination reduces operating performance. There are many academic studies on human capital and core competencies.

According to Wright et al. (1998), existing core competencies do not affect the refineries' performance. Lack of Core competencies reduces the performance of refineries. So while good management may not always work well, bad management certainly harms the business.

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According to Thomas and Feldman (2010), competitive core skills mediate the impact of both training and organizational tenure on in-role and non-role work performance. Job performance positively affects employees' salaries and promotions. Marimuthu et al. (2009) companies should strengthen their human capital to improve their operating performance. According to Marr et al. (2004), a long-term competitive advantage can only be derived from the management of information assets underlying their organizational capabilities and the good management of human capital. For strengthening human capital, there should be discrimination in the workplace during the promotion stage. In their work for Balkan countries, Yilmaz and Demirhan (2016) found that human capital indicators contributed to both economic growth and labor productivity. Sa'Enz (2005) examined the relationship between human capital and companies' market book value ratio. The results show a clear positive relationship between human capital indicators and market book value. There is a high correlation between the efficiency of banks and financial return. While the results of the studies that we're observing the relationship between human capital and performance are precise, good management and rational management require accurate measurement and fair analysis in decision-making. Precise measurement can be done by balancing scorecards in a business. Performing the analysis with equitable criteria naturally improves performance.

5. OVERVIEW & DIFFERENT PERSPECTIVES OF DISCRIMINATION WORKPLACE DISCRIMINATION

Discrimination is such a broad subject that it has been the subject of countless novels and films. For instance, in romantic dramas "Romeo & Juliet" and "Ferhat & Şirin" etc., and in cowboy movies, discrimination was the movie's central theme. Rich and powerful cowboy rules others. He decides: he determines the rules, wants others to comply with his rules, but he does obey his own rules. Their rules are different. The powerful and rich cowboy decides about the rules, does not comply, and wants others to follow them. Discrimination is the application of specified rules (law) to different people in different places and times.

In this study, discrimination is "the collection of decisions and practices which are not based on fair criteria, whose fair criterions intentionally neglected, which the criteria are not measured and analyzed correctly, which offend the law, religion, human beliefs and efficiency of the company, which are harming the business, victims, victims' families financially and morally." There are four essential elements in this definition. These are (1) serious mistakes or the intentional neglect of fairness criteria, (2) serious mistakes or intentional neglect to failure measuring the criteria accurately, (3) existence of suffering parties: business, employees, public. (4) existence of ill-gotten gain parties.

Besides, types of discrimination can be overviewed from different perspectives such as:

5.1. Changing the Game Rules During the Match: rule maker (decision-maker) can change the rules repeatedly, let's say three times. When the victim complies with the first requirement, more requirements are added to the second requirement. When the victim complies with the second rule, the perpetrator can add more conditions to the third requirement. Sooner or later victim has to give up.

5.2. Denial of Vested Rights: theoretically, vested rights cannot be revoked retroactively. But perpetrators' economic and legal power and enforcement can force the victims to accept perpetrators' Denial of vested rights. When they change the game's rules during the match, they have to accept it for not to lose the job.

5.3. Double Standard Discrimination: perpetrators can use double, triple, and quartet standards for the victims. For instance, for the first victim (candidate), standard A is used, for the second candidate, standard B can be used, and maybe for the third candidate, standard C can be used, and in some cases for the fourth candidate, standard D can be used. Double standard criteria can be classified and realized under three bases: time-based double standards, person-based double standards, geographic-based double standards.

5.3.1. Time-Based Double Standards; the conditions of the promotion (exam or criterion) can be more difficult or accessible according to the purpose of the perpetrators. For instance, some employees can be promoted with 6 points, but the person promoted with six points can increase the limit to 100 points. While the perpetrator protects the title and benefits, a victim may not struggle to complete the requirements. Thanks to time-based double standards, no competition, uncomplicated life.

5.3.2. Personal Based Double Standards; perpetrators can use a different standard for Candidates because of the victims' appearances, language, race, political, religious beliefs. Hence perpetrator can eliminate the victim.

5.3.3. Geographic-Based Double Standards; In some cases, businesses may apply the promotion criteria, and standards differ in different geographical regions. In neglected geographical areas, it can be exceptionally acceptable up to a point. However, the

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decision-maker should be able to state the basis of decisions clearly. In similar geographies, using double standards should be questioned by the prosecutors, governing bodies.

5.3.4. Tutelage Discrimination (Hitman): discriminating on behalf of other people or other organizations. Indeed, hitman doesn't directly plan and benefit from the discrimination. Other persons are masterminds. Thus, it is not easy to reveal the discrimination; the perpetrator is different from planning and benefitting parties. Easy to cover.

5.3.5. Unknown Perpetrator: unidentified discrimination: here, perpetrators hide their identifications from the public. They don't announce their decisions publicly. If they have to, they don't give their open names. They only announce the name of the committee. To reach officially signed papers is not easy for not to be identified by the related bodies. In an incident, after a meeting by five members, the controversial decision has passed. Three of the members said they did not say yes to the decision while the other two did not comment, so who took the decision. Perpetrators always try to hide by not giving any clue; identification. Whenever there is no identity, it is called unidentified discrimination.

5.3.6. Using Promotional Discrimination as Carrot and Stick: although it is not in accordance with fairness, humanitarian law and religious discrimination based on carrot-stick theory, unfortunately, works very well. When carrots are shown, most employees do the desired behavior even if it is not on their behalf. Similarly, stick prevents their behaviors. Especially handicapped, weak, unprotected individuals influenced by carrots and sticks.

5.3.7. Intentionally not to Promote Anyone: the perpetrator has not been promoted to anyone in an incidence. Because the candidates were not going along with the other unofficial group, even though the candidates' suited the job requirements. Here, all the parties, including decision-makers, should be loyal to the business or organization where they earn their lives, not to other organizations.

5.3.8. Institutional and non-Institutional Discrimination; Decision-makers in institutional discrimination know unwritten discrimination rules. Even they made the rules; no one proved them because there is no concrete evidence. Who will be promoted or not is determined by the Unwritten, secret promotion rules? Everyone knows these rules, including the victims, but they cannot object, they cannot say anything, and they have to accept the reality. On the other hand, in non-institutional discrimination organizations' other departments (internal auditors, chief executives and labor unions, etc.) can independently stand against discrimination and may not accept the unfair decisions and practices.

5.3.9. Systematic and Unsystematic Discrimination: in Systematic Institutional Discrimination, unfair decisions and practices are accepted by the whole system and continuously (matic) is practiced on the victims. Unfair decisions are taken systematically and automatically. If an employee who is mainly working as an account and who will be taking accounting exam for the promotion, have to work in the marketing department systematically, will not be able to have enough experience in accounting and will have lower points in the exam than another employee who worked in accounting department all the time. Unsystematic discrimination is usually faced once or twice all through the working period and is not repeated frequently.

5.3.10. Hiding and Camouflaging the Pandora's Box (Perfect Crime): perpetrator(s) can notify very high admission requirements or apply a challenging exam to everyone: fair enough. Most victims may give up even before applying because taking the exam is a stressful and money-consuming job. So high application fees and far exam places and psychiatric examiners can be a big barrier. The victim may give up taking the exam or may not apply to the post. Some of the victims were easily eliminated; excluded; the game was finished before it started. When the assessment time comes, promotion criteria can be lowered, and the favored person gets everything; others can be excluded. All proofs: ads, regulations, and communique related to promotion are instantly is hidden, camouflaged into Pandora's box. In some other cases, even though the exam results do not fit with the requirements, the favored person wins, but victims cannot look at the pandora's box: exam papers. In some other cases, even though the favored person's file may not contain the required papers, they can victimize the others; because pandora's box is not visible. However, rules applied only to the victims, not to the Perpetrators' beneficiaries. But pandora's box: files, exam papers, application requirements, are hidden and cannot be controlled, confirmed by trusted independent auditors. Auditors mostly focus on financial papers; they are usually staying away from pandora's box. For fair assessment, there shouldn't be any magical pandora's box where evil secrets are hidden. All the ads, communique, requirements should be visible. All the parties should be able to see, monitor, compare and assess these documents. A magical pandora's box can be considered as a sign of evil activities.

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6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

By nature, nepotism, corruption, and cheating, especially discrimination, take part in business life and are the workplace's most controversial issues. During a personal conversation, an executive manager stated that discrimination, nepotism, corruption, cheating, and, as a result, the injustice that used to exist in the past, still exists today, will happen in the future, instead of correcting them, you should be used to the situation, don't oppose them, get used to them, and take advantage of them."

Even though this is a horrible comment in the name of law & order, in the name of humanity, in the name of religion, and better management, it also contains truths. Unfortunately, discrimination (in the workplace) existed in the past, is still existing, and most probably it will exist in the future. That is why discrimination is so popular in the academic area: there were studies about workplace discrimination, which is already and will be in the future. Because size, place, severeness, types of discrimination evolving, changing like a virus. Every evolution requires new studies to identify, diagnose and treat legal, religious, humanitarian, administrative sickness instead of taking advantage of sickness.

The main justifications of the opposition against discrimination are explained under four headings in the study. It is believed that; Honorable people have to fight discrimination in the name of law & order, in the name of humanity, in the name of religion, and in the name of better management. Discriminators who are unfairly making the lives of innocent employees' (their children and partners) hell, have to be punished by the law, religion, humanity, and management for divine and eternal justice.

While any other discrimination usually occurs once or twice in a lifetime, the discrimination results during the promotion might harm and extort the victims' lives, living conditions, and earnings repeatedly. From this point of view, the injustice committed during the promotion is more and more constitutional crime, is more and more sin, is more and more crime against humanity, and is more and more harmful to the company's efficiency. It affects not only an employee but also his wife, his children, his entire family.

This study also classified ten different types of discrimination. These are Changing the rules of the game during the match, Denial of vested rights, double standard discrimination, time-based double standards, personal based double standards, geographic-based double standards, tutelage discrimination (hitman), unknown perpetrator: unidentified Discrimination, Using promotional Discrimination as Carrot and stick, Intentionally Not to promote anyone, institutional and non-institutional discrimination, Systematic and unsystematic discrimination, camouflaging the pandora's box (perfect discrimination: crime).

In risk management identifying the risks are vital for taking appropriate precautions. Early warnings and deciding on appropriate criteria like (worthiness) would lead the decision-makers to make fair decisions. Under the Worthiness criterion, there are three basic headings. These are education, experience, and loyalty. The worthiness criterion leads the auditors (prosecutors) to find any inappropriate or illegal decisions for correction and punishment.

Obviously, there is a strong need for further studies on discrimination during the promotion stage, like; managerial decision-making techniques to explore discrimination during the promotion stage.

There used to be (unfairness) discrimination during the promotion stages in the past. There is still, and unfortunately, there will be discrimination during the promotion. This process changes and evolves like harmful viruses. This study tried to explain and identify old and new versions of evil and harmful Sociological virus: workplace discrimination during the promotion. The study suggests, Honest, honorable, and faithful people must fight this evil and harmful Sociological virus in the name of law, in the name of humanity, in the name of religion, and in the name of good governance. We shall overcome injustice and all kinds of discrimination.

REFERENCES

- 1) Amaro, H., Russo, N. F., & Johnson, J. (1987). Family and Work Predictors of Psychological Well-Being Among Hispanic Women Professionals. *Psychol Women, Sayı. 11*, 505–521,.
- 2) American Convention On Human Rights "Pact Of San Jose, Costa Rica
https://www.oas.org/Dil/Access_To_Information_American_Convention_On_Human_Rights.Pdf (Erişim Tarihi: 01-07-2021).
- 3) Atkinson, A. B. (1971). *The Economics of Inequality* 146 (2nd Ed., Clarendon Press 1983) (1975) (Citing P.B. Doeringer & M.J. Piore, *Internal Labor Markets and Manpower Analysis*).
- 4) Brouwers, EPM, Mathijssen J, Van Bortel T, Knifton L. (2015) Discrimination in the Workplace, Reported by People With Major Depressive Disorder: A Cross-Sectional Study in 35 Countries. *BMJ Open* 2016;6:E009961. Doi:10.1136/Bmjopen-2015-009961 (Erişim Tarihi: 01-06-2021).
- 5) Burkard, A. W., Boticki, M. A., & Madson, M. B. (2002). Workplace Discrimination, Prejudice, and Diversity Measurement: a Review of Instrumentation. *Journal of Career Assessment*, Vol. 10 No. 3, 343–361

Standing Against to Workplace Discrimination (In the Name of Law & Order, Humanity, Religion, and Better Management): A Literature Review

- 6) Chung, Y. B., & Harmon, L. W. (1999). Assessment of Perceived Occupational Opportunity for Black Americans. *Journal of Career Assessment*, 7, 45-62.
- 7) Clapham, A. (2006) *Human Rights Obligations of the Non-State Actors*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- 8) Constitution of the Republic of Turkey: TÜRKİYE CUMHURİYETİ ANAYASASI Kanun No.: 2709 Kabul Tarihi: 7.11.1982, 20/10/1982 Tarihli Ve 17844 Sayılı Resmî Gazete’de Yayımlanana Anayasa Metni https://www.tbmm.gov.tr/anayasa/anayasa_2018.pdf (Erişim Tarihi: 01-06-2021).
- 9) Demiral, C. (2005) “4857 Sayılı İş Kanunu’nda Cinsiyet Ayrımcılığı”, E – Akademi Hukuk, Ekonomi & Siyasal Bilimler İnternet Dergisi, Sayı. 37, Ss. 21- 22.
- 10) European Convention on Human Rights (Rome, 4.XI.1950), https://www.echr.coe.int/documents/convention_eng.pdf
- 11) Friedman, M (1970). "The Social Responsibility of Business is to Increase Its Profits," *New York Times Magazine*.
- 12) Friedman, M., (1970) A theoretical framework for monetary analysis. *J. Polit. Econ.* 78, 193–238.
- 13) Ghumman, S., Ryan, A. M., Barclay, L. A., & Markel, K. S. (2013). Religious discrimination in the workplace: A review and examination of current and future trends. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 28, 439-454.
- 14) Hegarty, W. H., & Dalton, D. R. (1995). Development and Psychometric Properties of the Organizational Diversity Inventory (ODI). *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 55, 1047-1052.
- 15) Hodge, D. R. (2006). Moving Toward a More Inclusive Educational Environment? a Multi-Sample Exploration of Religious Discrimination as Seen Through the Eyes of Students from Various Faith Traditions. *Journal of Social Work Education*, 42, 249-267.
- 16) Hultin, M. (1998). Gender Differences in Workplace Authority: Discrimination and the Role of Organizational leaders, *Acta Sociologica*, Vol. 41, No. 2, Ss. 99-113.
- 17) International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1966) Adopted and Opened for Signature, Ratification and Accession by General Assembly Resolution 2200A (XXI) of 16 December 1966 <https://www.ohchr.org/Documents/ProfessionalInterest/Cescr.pdf> (Erişim Tarihi: 01-06-2021).
- 18) International Criminal Court (2002) <https://www.icc-cpi.int/about>
- 19) James K, Lovato C & Cropanzano R (1994) Correlational and Known-Group Comparison Validation of a Workplace Prejudice Discrimination Inventory, *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 24, 17, Ss. 157~7-1592.
- 20) James S. A., LaCroix A. Z. & Kleinbaum D.G. (1984). John Henryism and Blood Pressure Differences Among Black Men. II. The Role Of Occupational Stressors. *J. Behav. Med.* 7: 259–275.
- 21) Jolson, M. A. (1974). Employment Barriers in Marketing. *Journal of Marketing*, 38, 67-74
- 22) Karagöz, V. (2012). İş Hukukunda Ayrımcılık Tazminatı. *Erzincan Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, v:1 Pp. 57-76.
- 23) Kelman, M. (1991) Concepts of Discrimination in "General Ability" Job Testing, *Harvard Law Review*, Vol. 104, No. 6, Pp. 1157-1247.
- 24) King, E. B., & Ahmad, A. S. (2010). An Experimental Field Study Of İnterpersonal Discrimination Toward Muslim Job Applicants. *Personnel Psychology*, 63, 881-906.
- 25) Krieger, N. (1990) Racial and Gender Discrimination: Risk Factors For High Blood Pressure? *Soc. Sci. Med.* 30: 1273–1281.
- 26) Krieger, N. (1999). Embodying Inequality: A Review of Concepts, Measures, and Methods for Studying Health Consequences of Discrimination. *International Journal of Health Services* 29: 295-352
- 27) Kuran: <https://kuran.diyaret.gov.tr/tefsir/> (Erişim Tarihi: 01-06-2021).
- 28) Larkey, L. K., (1996) The Development and Validation of the Workforce Diversity Questionnaire: An Instrument to Assess Interactions in Diverse Groups, *Management Communication Quarterly*, 9(3), pg. 296-337.
- 29) Lofaso A. M. (2017) Workers' Rights as Natural Human Rights, *University of Miami Law Review*, 4-24, 564-524.
- 30) Lofaso, A. M. (2007) Toward a Foundational Theory of Workers' Rights: The Autonomous Dignified Worker, *UMKC LAW REVIEW*, No. 75. Ss. 1-65.
- 31) Marimuthu, M., Arokiasamy, L. & Ismail, M. (2009) Human Capital Development and Its Impact on Firm Performance: Evidence From Developmental Economics. *The Journal of International Social Research*, Volume 2/8. Ss.265-272.
- 32) Marr, B., Schiuma, G. & Neely, A., (2004). Intellectual capital and knowledge management effectiveness. *Business Process Management Journal*, Vol:10 No:5 Ss 551-569
- 33) Montei, M. S., Adams, G.,A. & Eggers L., M. (1996). Validity of Scores on the Attitudes toward Diversity Scale (ATDS) educational and psychological measurement, Sayı. 56 issue 2.

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- 34) Murrell, N. L. (1996). Stress, Self-Esteem, and Racism: Relationships with Low Birth Weight and Preterm Delivery in African American Women. *J. Natl. Black Nurses Assoc.* 8: 45–53.
- 35) Sa'Enz J. (2005) Human Capital İndicators, Business Performance and Market-to-Book Ratio, *Journal of Intellectual Capital*. Sayı. 6 No. 3, Ss. 374-384
- 36) Santora, J. C., & Seaton, W. J. (2008), Age Discrimination: Alive and Well in the Workplace? *Academy of Management Perspectives*, Vol. 22, No. 2 Pp. 103-104.
- 37) Somuncu K, İlter B, Yılmaz C, and Kaymaz A. R, (2015) Kadınların Muhasebe Mesleğindeki Girişimciliğini Engelleyen Unsurlar, *Uluslararası Katılımlı Sosyal Yaşam ve Kadın Sempozyumu*, 21-22 Aralık, Konya, pp: 325-340.
- 38) Sperino, S. F. (2011), Rethinking Discrimination Law, *Michigan Law Review*, October 2011, Vol. 110, No. 1 Ss. 69-125
- 39) The Equal Employment Opportunity Commission (2011) Eşit İstihdam Fırsatı heyeti: <https://www.eeoc.gov/federal-sector/reports/equal-employment-opportunity-commission-eeoc-fy-2011-eeo-complaint>.
- 40) The European Convention on Human Rights (Rome, 4.XI.1950) https://www.echr.coe.int/documents/convention_eng.pdf.
- 41) The International Labour Office; Convention No. 111. See 22.05.1967 Tarihli ve 12602 Sayılı Resmi Gazete ve Ek Kararname İçin Bkz. 21.09.1967 ve 12705 Sayılı Resmi Gazete. Sözleşme'nin Resmi Türkçe Adı "İş ve Meslek Bakımından Ayırım Hakkında Sözleşme" Şeklinde dir
- 42) The Social Accountability 8000 Standard Web Page [www.Sa-İntl.Org/Sa8000.html](http://www.sa-intl.org/Sa8000.html)
- 43) Thomas W. H. & Feldman, D. C. (2010). Human Capital and Objective İndicators of Career Success: The Mediating Effects of Cognitive Ability and Conscientiousness. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology* 83, 207–235
- 44) Thorat, S. & Newman, K. S. (2007) Caste and Economic Discrimination: Causes, Consequences and Remedies, *Economic and Political Weekly*, - 19, 2007, Vol. 42, No.- 19, Ss. 4121-4124
- 45) Thyer, B., & Myers, L. (2009). Religion Discrimination in Social Work Academic Programs: Whither Social Justice? *Journal of Religion and Spirituality in Social Work: Social Thought*, 28, 144.
- 46) Turkish Labor Law: İŞ KANUNU Kanun Numarası : 4857 Kabul Tarihi : 22/5/2003 Yayımlandığı Resmî Gazete : Tarih : 10/6/2003 Sayı : 25134 Yayımlandığı Düstur : Tertip : 5 Cilt : 42 <https://www.mevzuat.gov.tr/Mevzuatmetin/1.5.4857.Pdf> (Erişim Tarihi: 01-06-2021).
- 47) Turkish Unions law Act 2821. Sendikalar Kanunu, Kanun Numarası : 2821 Kabul Tarihi : 5/5/1983 Yayımlandığı R. Gazete : Tarih : 7/5/1983 Sayı : 18040 Yayımlandığı Düstur : Tertip : 5 Cilt : 22 Sayfa : 316 <https://www.mevzuat.gov.tr/Mevzuatmetin/1.5.2821.Pdf> (Erişim Tarihi: 01-06-2021).
- 48) United Nations (1948) United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights <https://www.jus.uio.no/lm/en/pdf/un.universal.declaration.of.human.rights.1948.portrait.letter.pdf>. (Erişim Tarihi: 01-06-2021).
- 49) Wolf, W. C. & Fligstein. N. D. (1979). Sexual Stratification: Differences in Power in The Work Setting. *Social Forces*, 58. 94-107.
- 50) Wright P. M., McMahan G. C., McCormick, B & Sherman W. S.t (1998) Strategy, Core Competence, and HR Involvement as Determinants of HR Effectiveness and Refinery Performance, *Human Resource Management*, Spring, Vol. 37, No. 1, Ss. 17–29
- 51) Wright, E. O., Baxter, J. & Birkelund, G. E. (1995). The Gender Gap in Workplace Authority in Seven Nations. *American Sociological Review*, 60, 407 - 435.
- 52) Yılmaz, C. & Demirhan, B. (2016) Long-Term Impact of Human Capital on Economic Growth: A Panel Data Analysis on the Balkan Countries, *British Journal Of Economics, Management & Trade*, 13(1): 1-12,